

Parental Attachment and Love Attitudes: A Comparative Study among Gen-Z Young Adults Having Single Working Parents and both Working Parents in India

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In modern India, the growing prevalence of dual-income families and single working parent households is reshaping the emotional development of Gen-Z individuals aged 18-25, particularly in how they form beliefs about trust, communication, and love. This study aimed to examine and compare parental attachment and love attitudes among Gen-Z young adults from two family structures: single working parent households and those with both parents working. A total of 122 participants (60 from single working parent families & 62 from dual-working-parent families) were selected through purposive sampling from academic and corporate settings across India. Using standardized tools the Inventory of Parent and Peer Attachment-Revised (Gullone & Robinson, 2005) and the Love Attitudes Scale Short Form (Hendrick & Hendrick, 1986) data were collected between April 20 and May 23, 2025. Independent-sample t-tests revealed significant differences in paternal attachment dimensions: father trust ($p = .009$), father communication ($p = .004$), and father alienation ($p = .004$), with higher scores reported by participants from single working parent households. A notable difference was also found in the Ludus love style ($p = .038$), which was higher among those from dual-working-parent families. Maternal attachment and other love styles showed no significant variation between the groups. These findings suggest that family structure, particularly the quality of father-child relationships, plays a crucial role in shaping Gen-Z individuals' emotional and romantic expectations. The results underscore the importance of understanding the nuanced ways in which evolving parental roles influence young adults' perceptions of attachment and love in contemporary Indian society.

Keywords: Parental attachment, generation Z, family structure, love attitudes, single working parent, both working parents

What happens when the people meant to teach us love are too busy surviving to show it?

In the fast-changing socio-economic structure of modern India, Gen-Z youth-those born between the mid-1990s to late 2000s reside in the connection of the real and virtual worlds. They are "always connected, computer-savvy, communicative, content-wise, community-oriented, and change-accepting" (Świerkosz-Hołyś, 2016; Hysa, 2016; Dolot, 2018). Some scholars have even referred to them as the "R-Generation" (Csobanka, 2016), highlighting their sense of duty in the face of world turmoil. People from Generation Z are quietly navigating emotional and relational landscapes shaped not just by culture or peers, but more deeply by the kind of parenting they receive at home. The family structure and emotional availability of caregivers are changing dramatically as the workforce grows and more parents pursue full-time jobs. Indian families are undergoing a quiet transformation. The traditional image of a mother available at home and a father as the primary breadwinner is no longer a

consistent norm. A growing percentage of households are made up of dual-income working parents or are led by a single working parent. These changes are not solely economic; they also affect the upbringing, romantic feelings, and overall capacity for love among young people. A study was conducted to examine how gender and parenting styles affect rejection sensitivity in Indian Gen-Z young people, which found that while authoritarian parenting was associated with higher levels of emotional vulnerability, authoritative parenting was associated with lower rejection sensitivity. Notably, this study found that while men scored higher on rejection sensitivity, women reported experiencing more of the three parenting philosophies-authoritarian, permissive, and authoritative. These findings demonstrate how parenting styles can influence emotional resilience based on a person's gender (Sawal et al., 2024).

Bowlby and Ainsworth: Foundations in Attachment

According to John Bowlby in 1988, attachment is a "lasting psychological connectedness between human beings", an evolutionary push in infants to pursue caregiver safety. He discussed internal working models (IWMs), which are mental maps of oneself and others created by early caregiving and have an impact on relationships in the future. Bowlby also found four attachment patterns: secure, anxious-ambivalent, avoidant, and disorganized. In 1978, Mary Ainsworth built on his research by creating the Strange Situation, revealing three patterns of attachment:

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Secure: child distressed when caregiver departs, rapidly comforted on return;

Avoidant: expresses minimal affects, even in solitude;

Anxious-ambivalent: extremely disturbed, mixed reactions at reunion.

Parental Attachment: Trust, Communication, Alienation:

Grounded in Bowlby's theory, attachment is the lifelong emotional connection that affects psychosocial functioning throughout an individual's life. This study draws reference to Armsden and Greenberg's (1987) multidimensional conceptualization, which comprises -

Parent Trust: mutual understanding and respect between parent and adolescent;

Parent Communication: open two-way dialogue shaping social understanding;

Parent Alienation: feelings of isolation or hostility-emotional distance from the parent.

According to Indian studies on attachment, toddlers have a 95% secure attachment rate. However, patterns in adolescents and young adults are not thoroughly studied, particularly when it comes to parental work schedules (Kayastha et al., 2010). These elements, which reaffirm classic attachment theory, are essential to comprehending how teenagers interpret their parents' relationships to shape their own love relationships in the future. A study investigated the effects of parental attachment and depressive symptoms on relationships among 196 young adults in their early twenties, which indicates that emotional support and romantic relationship satisfaction were positively correlated with a stable bond to one's mother. Conversely, depression symptoms were associated with more conflict and criticism in friendships, particularly among men. The combined effects of parental ties and emotional well-being on interpersonal functioning are highlighted in this study (Fadli et al., 2024). Another large cross-sectional study conducted in China, which involved over a thousand adolescents, indicates how interparental conflict and attachment relate to suicidal ideation. In this study, findings showed that strong parental conflict increased suicide ideation, while secure attachments to both parents reduced this risk. It is interesting to note in their study that adolescents from rural areas appeared less vulnerable than their urban peers. In this study researchers focused that improving parent-child relationships and reducing family conflict could play a protective role in adolescent mental health (Wang et al., 2024). Sholekhah and Pertiwi (2024) conducted a study to compare parental attachment styles of adolescents within matrilineal (Minangkabau) and patrilineal (Batak) backgrounds in Indonesia. They discovered there was no significant difference between the two cultural groups and have moderate attachment levels using the IPPA-R. However, regardless of their ancestry, adolescents in this study had a stronger attachment to their mothers, and trust and communication were the most significant predictors of parental attachment.

Lee's (1973) Love Attitudes

According to John Alan Lee's typology of love, there are six distinct styles that affect how people perceive, interact with, and manage romantic relationships. They are Eros, who is dynamic and intense

and usually based on physical attraction and idealization of the loved one; Ludus, who is playful and game-like and where love is informal and non-committal; and Storge, who develops gradually from intimate friendship and emotional intimacy. Other varieties include Agape, which is selfless and altruistic and prioritizes the needs of one's partner over one's own; Mania, which is marked by emotional highs and lows, obsession, and possessiveness; and Pragma, which is pragmatic and grounded in reason, compatibility, and shared life goals.

Hendrick and Hendrick (1986) later shifted these into the six-style model of love attitudes, which are cognitive templates that influence the way people think and act in romantic situations. These are not solely inclinations but are profoundly influenced by early attachment experiences, with childhood and adolescence being key. Through what Bowlby (1988) described as internal working models, our early relationships-particularly those with parents-create a psychological anchor that shapes the way we receive and express love during emerging adulthood. A Portuguese study was conducted among 1153 adults, which examined the psychometric properties of the LAS-SF and how its six love styles related to romantic outcomes. Among the love styles assessed in this study, Eros (passionate love) was strongly associated with lower romantic loneliness and higher sexual desire, commitment, and love life satisfaction. On the other hand, ludus (playful love) had a negative correlation with commitment and a good correlation with romantic loneliness. While pragma, or practical love, was also connected with romantic loneliness, it's interesting to note that mania, or possessive love, and storge, or friendship-based love, both predicted higher levels of commitment. Selfless love, or agape, has a positive correlation with commitment and satisfaction but has a negative correlation with loneliness. Furthermore, this study also found that commitment acted as a mediator in the relationship between agape and romantic loneliness, showing how deeply relational commitment and selfless love might reduce emotions of alienation (Neto et al., 2025). Another study explored the connection between depression and love attitudes among 400 university students in Istanbul. They found that students who supported more passionate love styles tended to report lower levels of depression using the LAS-SF and the Beck Depression Inventory. On the other hand, higher depression scores were positively correlated with possessiveness (Mania) and (Ludus) love styles. Depressive symptoms were not significantly correlated with other types of love (Sirin et al., 2015).

Socio-cultural Factors Influencing Gen-Z Attachment and Love

In India, Gen-Z is growing up presence of changing family responsibilities, ongoing digital exposure, and unstable economic conditions. Young adults may have more responsibility at home when both parents are frequently employed, which may affect their family dynamics and communication. Additionally, social media adds pressure by projecting idealized ideals of success and love. Cross-cultural realities, such as parental authority, could conflict with Gen-Z's growing independence. Relationships between parents and children can be improved or weakened by economic stresses like the expense of education or parental job ambiguity. A qualitative study of Gen-Z participants in Sri Lanka, who ranged in age from 18 to 26, found that attitudes on marriage and love were evolving. In previous generations, love was considered a social obligation; today,

it is considered a necessity for marriage. Declining marriage rates are connected to these changing perceptions, which are marked by emotional boundaries and individualism. This indicates that South Asian culture is evolving more broadly. It suggests that evolving views on love may be changing attachment patterns and romantic expectations among Gen-Z people (Kulathunga & Abeysinghe, 2024).

Research Gap

Secure parental attachment is consistently associated with healthier emotional and romantic development (Li et al., 2020). However, most existing studies are based in countries such as Portugal, China, and Indonesia, where family structures, cultural norms, and interpersonal expectations differ significantly from those in India. As Indian Gen-Z youth are shaped by collectivistic values, multigenerational households, and unique societal pressures, these cross-cultural differences limit the generalizability of prior findings. This highlights a critical research gap and the need for culturally contextualized studies on parental attachment and romantic development in the Indian context.

In South Asia, limited research has examined how specific dimensions of parental attachment—such as trust, emotional closeness, and communication—shape young adults' beliefs about love and romantic relationships. While some studies have linked parental bonds to mental health and peer connections (Kayastha et al., 2010) attachment is often treated as a singular, generalized construct. This overlooks nuanced elements that may significantly influence how Gen-Z individuals navigate intimacy and emotional connections in romantic contexts.

Additionally, while love styles such as Eros, Ludus, or Agape have been studied widely, there is limited understanding of how these romantic attitudes are shaped by parenting experiences in India, especially for those just entering serious relationships.

Family structure is another area that's often missed out. With many Indian youth now raised by either single working parents or dual working parents, it's important to ask how these household dynamics impact attachment and, in turn, romantic thinking.

This study addresses these gaps by exploring how parental attachment subdomains vary across different family structures and how they influence love attitudes among Indian Gen-Z individuals.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to explore and compare parental attachment and love attitudes among the Gen-Z young adult population living with both parents (single working parent and both working parents) in India. This study follows a cross-sectional research design and adopts a quantitative research method.

Objectives of the Study

- To explore and find the significant differences, if any, in mother attachment (Parent Trust, Parent Communication, Parent Alienation) among the Gen-Z population having single working parents and both working parents in India.
- To explore and find the significant differences, if any, in father attachment (Parent Trust, Parent Communication, Parent Alienation) among the Gen-Z population having single working parents and both working parents in India.
- To explore and to find the significant differences, if any, in love attitudes (Eros, Ludus, Storge, Mania, Pragma, & Agape) among

the Gen-Z population having single working parents and both working parents in India.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There is no significant difference with respect to mother attachment (Parent Trust, Parent Communication, Parent Alienation) among the Gen-Z population having single working parents and both working parents.
- There is no significant difference with respect to father attachment (Parent Trust, Parent Communication, Parent Alienation) among the Gen-Z population having single working parents and both working parents.
- There is no significant difference with respect to love attitudes (Eros, Ludus, Storge, Mania, Pragma, & Agape) among the Gen-Z population having single working parents and both working parents in India.

Method

Participants

The study comprised a total of 122 young Gen-Z adults, aged between 18 and 25 years, who were systematically categorized based on their household parental work structure. The sample was initially divided into two primary groups: the first group included 60 participants residing in households where only one parent is working, specifically the father, while the second group consisted of 62 participants from households where both parents are employed. The mean age of participants across both the single-working-parent and dual-working-parent groups was 21.34 years ($SD = 2.13$).

Inclusion Criteria: The study included Gen-Z young adults (aged 18-25 years) from middle socio-demographic backgrounds, who had completed at least 12th grade, lived with their biological family, and were proficient in English. Participants came from households with either one working parent or both working parents, and consented to take part in the research.

Exclusion Criteria: Participants were excluded if they had a deceased parent, lived with only one parent, had a history of psychiatric illness, substance use during assessment, suicidal thoughts or attempts, or any physical disability.

Variables

Parental Attachment: Parental attachment refers to the deep emotional bond that develops between a child and their primary caregiver, characterized by feelings of security, trust, and protection. This connection shapes the child's sense of safety and forms the foundation of their emotional and relational development.

Love Attitudes: Love attitudes are individuals' enduring cognitive frameworks about romantic relationships, encapsulating six distinct styles—Eros, Ludus, Storge, Mania, Pragma, and Agape—as identified by Hendrick and Hendrick (1986). These attitudes reflect how one perceives, experiences, and behaves in love, influencing emotions, expectations, and relationship dynamics.

Sampling Techniques

In this study, Purposive sampling is used for the selection of the sample because the selection is done according to some inclusion and exclusion criteria to serve the purpose of the study. Purposive sampling is a non-random method where researchers intentionally select participants based on specific traits or criteria relevant to the

study. It's useful for targeting a particular group but may not represent the larger population.

Measures

Consent Form: Before beginning the assessment, participants were given a consent form outlining the study's purpose, their rights, and the voluntary nature of participation. Only after their consent, a semi-structured socio-demographic form was used to collect key background details like age, education, family setup, parental occupation, income, and health history, ensuring they fit the study's criteria and context.

Socio-demographic Sheet: A semi-structured socio-demographic sheet was used to gather essential background information from participants. This included age, gender, household structure (single or both working parents) and history of any severe physical illness, history of any psychiatric illness, and family history of any psychiatric illness of the young adult.

Inventory of Parent and Peer Attachment Revised (IPPA-R), created by Gullone and Robinson (2005) and adapted from Armsden and Greenberg (1987) was used to assess the quality of the participants' attachment with their parents. The version used in this study focused solely on parental attachment and included three subscales: Trust, Communication, and Alienation. Responses were rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with a mix of direct and reverse-scored items. Higher scores in Trust and Communication indicate secure attachment, while higher scores in Alienation suggest emotional distance or conflict. The internal consistency of the scale ranges from $\alpha = .66$ to $.86$, reflecting good reliability.

Love Attitudes Scale - Short Form (LAS-SF) by Clyde and Hendrick (1986) based on Lee's theory (1973) was used to explore six styles of love: Eros, Ludus, Storge, Mania, Pragma, and Agape. The scale contains 24 items, with 4 items per subscale, rated on a 5-point Likert scale. There are no reverse-scored items, and each subscale score reflects how strongly the participant identifies with that love style.

The scale has shown solid psychometric strength, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from $.68$ to $.88$.

Procedure

Participants were personally approached and informed about the study's aim and process. Their involvement was fully voluntary, with both verbal and written consent collected beforehand. Data was gathered from colleges, universities, and corporate offices across India using purposive sampling. The collection took place between April 20 and May 23, 2025. Participants, who met the study's criteria, completed two standardized questionnaires-the IPPA-R (Gullone & Robinson, 2005) and LAS-SF (Hendrick & Hendrick, 1986) all in English, in a quiet, supportive setting. Afterward, responses were carefully reviewed, scored as per the manuals, coded, and prepared for analysis, with strict attention to confidentiality and accuracy.

Statistical Analysis

This study employed descriptive statistics such as Mean and Standard Deviation to explore all the variables among both groups, alongside inferential statistics including Independent t-test was conducted to measure the significant difference. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 was utilized for both descriptive and inferential analysis. The significance level chosen for this study was 0.05 level of significance for all two-tailed hypotheses.

Results

The following section outlines the statistical outcomes of the study. Descriptive statistics (Mean & Standard Deviation) were conducted to explain the parental attachment (Parent Trust, Parent Communication, Parent Alienation) and love attitudes (Eros, Ludus, Storge, Mania, Pragma, & Agape) among Gen Z young adults with single working parent and both working parents in the households.

Table 1

Mean and Standard Deviation of the above-mentioned variables among Gen-Z

Variables	Single working parent in the household (Mean & SD)	Both working parents in the household (Mean & SD)
Trust towards mother	39.9667 (7.90830)	38.4516 (7.42543)
Communication towards mother	31.4000 (7.90023)	30.0806 (7.47081)
Alienation towards mother	21.3500 (5.03151)	20.3871 (4.38834)
Trust towards father	38.0833 (10.62184)	32.9677 (10.53327)
Communication towards father	28.8667 (9.22316)	24.0000 (9.18302)
Alienation towards father	20.8667 (5.84392)	17.6290 (6.25217)
Eros	4.9667 (3.91852)	4.9516 (4.24815)
Ludus	8.0000 (.00000)	8.9355 (3.44926)
Storge	5.3000 (4.46569)	5.5484 (4.86094)
Mania	8.6000 (4.12598)	8.3548 (3.76392)
Pragma	5.7667 (4.05206)	6.0323 (3.98344)
Agape	6.1500 (4.67893)	6.3871 (4.22077)

Table 1 reveals that Gen-Z young adults with single working parents reported stronger parental attachment across both mother and father dimensions (Parent trust, Parent communication, & Parent alienation). They also showed slightly higher mean scores in the Eros ($M=4.97$ vs.

4.95) and Mania ($M = 8.60$ vs. 8.35) love attitudes. In contrast, participants with both working parents exhibited marginally higher mean scores in Ludus ($M=8.94$ vs. 8.00), Storge ($M=5.55$ vs. 5.30), Pragma ($M=6.03$ vs. 5.77), and Agape ($M=6.39$ vs. 6.15).

Figure 1

Mean Scores of Attachments towards Mother among the Gen-Z Young Adults, who Reside with Single Working Parents and both Working Parents in the Household

Figure 2

Mean Scores of Attachments towards Father among the Gen-Z Young Adults, who Reside with Single Working Parents and both Working Parents in the household

Figure 3

Mean Scores of Love Attitudes among the Gen-Z Young Adults, Reside with Single Working Parents and both Working Parents in the Household

Graphical representation of mean scores with respect to parental attachment and love attitudes among Gen-Z young adults having single working parents and both working parents in the households.

Inferential statistics (Independent sample t-test) was conducted to explore significant differences in parental attachment style and love attitudes (Eros, Ludus, Storge, Mania, Pragma, & Agape) among the Gen-Z population with single working parents and both working parents in the households.

Table 2 presents the results of independent-samples t-tests, indicating significant differences in paternal attachment between Gen-Z individuals with single working parents and those with both working parents. The single-working-parent group reported higher scores in father trust, communication, and alienation. Additionally, a significant difference was observed in the Ludus love style between the two groups.

Table 2

t-values, in Parental Attachment (Parent Trust, Parent Communication, Parent Alienation) and Love Attitudes (Eros, Ludus, Storge, Mania, Pragma, and Agape) among the Gen-Z Population with Single Working Parents and both Working Parents in the Households

Variables	Single working parent in the household (N = 60) (Mean)	Both working parents in the household (N = 62) (Mean)	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Trust towards mother	39.9667	38.4516	1.091	.277	Retain the null hypothesis
Communication towards mother	31.4000	30.0806	.948	.345	Retain the null hypothesis
Alienation towards mother	21.3500	20.3871	1.128	.262	Retain the null hypothesis
Trust towards father	38.0833	32.9677	2.671	.009**	Reject the null hypothesis
Communication towards father	28.8667	24.0000	2.920	.004**	Reject the null hypothesis
Alienation towards father	20.8667	17.6290	2.953	.004**	Reject the null hypothesis
Eros	4.9667	4.9516	.020	.984	Retain the null hypothesis
Ludus	8.0000	8.9355	-2.101	.038*	Reject the null hypothesis
Storge	5.3000	5.5484	-.294	.770	Retain the null hypothesis
Mania	8.6000	8.3548	.343	.732	Retain the null hypothesis
Pragma	5.7667	6.0323	-.365	.716	Retain the null hypothesis
Agape	6.1500	6.3871	-.294	.769	Retain the null hypothesis

Note. ** 0.01 level of significant *0.05 level of significant

Table 2 presents the results of independent-samples t-tests, indicating significant differences in paternal attachment between

Gen-Z individuals with single working parents and those with both working parents. The single-working-parent group reported higher

scores in father trust, communication, and alienation. Additionally, a significant difference was observed in the Ludus love style between the two groups.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to explore whether Gen Z young adults from two different family structures (single working parent households & both working parent households) show differences in their parental attachment (to mother & father) and their romantic love attitudes. Based on the data collected from 122 Gen Z individuals in India, some important patterns appeared, especially in the relationship to father attachment and Ludus love attitude.

Father Attachment Differences

One of the most noticeable findings of this study is the significant difference in father trust, communication, and alienation between the two groups (Gen Z with single working parents & both working parents). Gen Z participants who came from single working parent households showed notably different patterns in how they related to their fathers compared to those who had both parents working. This indicates that when only one parent is managing the home and work responsibilities, the role of the father may shift in ways that either improve or deteriorate the emotional bond.

These results echo the findings of Singh and Lal (2023) who found that while both parents play an important role in the emotional life of Indian youth, many respondents but especially women, reported feeling distant from their mothers. However, both genders reported having a stronger emotional connection with mothers than with fathers. In contrast, this study highlights that the fathers play a more dynamic role and are possibly more sensitive to changes in the family work dynamics.

In many Indian families, fathers are usually seen as providers rather than emotional caregivers. This traditional balance, however, may shift when only one parent is working in the household, which may require the fathers to take on more emotional and caregiving roles, which could create either opportunities to create secure bonding (through more communication & trust) or significant emotional distance if the father is unable to adapt to these changing roles. This could explain the differences in trust, communication, and alienation we observed in father-child relationships.

Additionally, Sholekhah and Pertiwi (2024) found that adolescents, regardless of cultural background, had stronger attachments to their mothers, with trust and communication being the significant factors of the attachment quality. In addition to supporting this, our findings demonstrate that father attachment deserves more attention, especially in Indian households where altered work schedules are changing the roles of both parents.

Love Attitudes and Ludus Style

The only significant difference found in love attitudes was in the Ludus. Ludus represents a playful, sometimes casual or game-like approach to romantic relationships. Participants from single working-parent households scored differently on this love style compared to those with both parents working.

It can be one possible interpretation that growing up with just one active caregiver may influence how individuals view emotional closeness and intimacy. Some might develop more cautious or adopt less committed romantic patterns as a protective mechanism, especially when their emotional needs were inconsistently met

during childhood. Others might turn to playful or avoidant love styles to avoid vulnerability.

These results stand with the findings from Fadli et al. (2024) who noted that emotional support, especially from mothers, was linked to healthier and more satisfying romantic relationships. On the other hand, a lack of emotional stability or the presence of depressive symptoms was connected to more conflict and insecurity in personal relationships, particularly in men. In the context of our findings, young adults who lack consistent father support may lean toward Ludus as a way to avoid emotional dependence or protect themselves from uncertainty.

No Significant Differences in Mother Attachment or Other Love Styles

It's important to note that this study could not find any significant differences in mother attachment or other love styles (Eros, Storge, Mania, Pragma, Agape) between the two groups (Gen Z with a single working parent & both working parents). This could indicate that mothers, whether they are single working parents or members of a dual-working household, continue to be relatively steady emotional figures.

This consistency may reflect the traditional Indian values where mothers, irrespective of their work status, are expected to maintain emotional closeness with their children. Sholekhah and Pertiwi (2024) also emphasised that adolescents, even across different cultural backgrounds, consistently showed stronger attachment to their mothers.

This study emphasized that family structure matters, but not in a uniform way. The emotional bond with fathers appears more sensitive to whether the household has one or two working parents. And in terms of romantic relationships, only certain love styles, like Ludus, seem to be affected by these early experiences. These findings suggest that father-child dynamics are evolving in India's changing family landscape and that understanding these shifts is crucial, not just for emotional development but also for how young adults approach love, trust, and intimacy in relationships.

Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of parental attachment and how it connects to romantic attitudes in Gen-Z young adults in India. The results showed clear differences in the father attachment (trust, communication & alienation) and the love style in ludus. These findings indicate that the presence and emotional involvement of parents, especially fathers, can shape how young adults form romantic beliefs and behaviors. It also shows that growing up in a single working parent household might influence the kind of emotional experiences and expectations young people carry into their relationships. By comparing two family types, the study adds to the growing research on how changing family roles in modern India are shaping the inner emotional world of young adults.

Limitations of the Study

Every study has its limitations, and this one is no exception:

Sample Size: While 122 participants provide useful insights, a larger sample across different regions of India could help make the findings more general.

Self-Report Measures: Participants answered questionnaires based on their perception. This may include bias or inaccurate memory.

Implications of the Study

Parenting Programs: The findings can help create awareness among parents, especially fathers, about the importance of emotional availability and open communication with their children.

Counseling and Guidance: School and college counselors can use these findings to better understand students' emotional and romantic struggles, especially those from single working parent households.

Relationship Education: Workshops that teach young adults about different love styles, communication skills, and healthy attachment can promote better romantic relationships and emotional health.

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